

ISic2750

I.Sicily inscription 2750

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332879

1. ἐνθάδε κ [εἶται]
2. Νώνιος Π ι [— — —]
3. τέκτων· κά λ [λιστόν]
4. ποτε τοῦτον [ἀ]νεῖ-
5. λε κίων καὶ Μοῖρα |
6. ὃς κατέλειψε πατρι
7. λύπην δεινοτάτην· |
8. ἔζησε ἔτη ιβ'.
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645153
EDCS 64901099
PHI 332879

Bibliography

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